

Kinetics of nitrate reduction in submerged soils

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The results of the nitrate reduction kinetics of laterite and alluvial soils of West Bengal, under different treatments, reveal that the $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ content in both the soils decreases with the time of submergence and follows an exponential pattern indicating first order of reaction kinetics irrespective of treatments. Also there is complete disappearance of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ in both the soils due to starch application at the end of 14 days of submergence. The rate of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ reduction is much higher in two soils treated with starch or nitrogen (KNO_3 or prilled urea) than that of the untreated soils resulting from the higher values of the velocity constants and shortening of half-life period as well as changes in pH and E_h in the treated soils.

Soil submergence coupled with the application of organic matter brings about various physicochemical, electrochemical, chemical and biological changes which affect the transformation of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ in soils¹⁻⁴. It has been reported⁵ that the critical redox potential (E_h) at which all $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ is reduced and Mn^{2+} first appears in the soil solution, is approximately at a redox value of 200 mV. Therefore, an understanding of the kinetics of transformation of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ in submerged soils is the important parameter in determining the fertilizer N efficiency in lowland rice. So the present investigation was undertaken to study the kinetics of nitrate transformation in submerged soils.

Results and Discussion

Changes in soil pH: The results (Table 1) show that in Haplaquepts soil (alluvial), there was a slight increase in pH during the first week of submergence in the treatment receiving no starch, whereas in soils receiving starch there was a decline in pH of the soil. However, the overall chan-

ges in pH values remained almost neutral irrespective of any treatment. In case of Haplustalfs soil (laterite), there was a gradual increase in pH with the progress of submergence and at the end of incubation period (35 days) the pH was almost near neutral like that of Haplaquepts soil. The increase in pH of Haplaquepts is due to the accumulation of ammonia resulting from comparatively higher rate of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ reduction and changes in $\text{Fe}^{2+}\text{-Fe}^{3+}$ equilibrium in soils⁶.

Changes in redox potential (E_h): The results (Table 2) show that the redox potential values in both the soils decrease from +148 to -125 and +120 to -90 mV respectively, with the progress of submergence. However, the application of starch caused a further decrease in E_h values in both the soils¹. The magnitude of decrease in the redox potential values was found to be greater in Haplaquepts soil compared to Haplustalfs, and this might be due to its higher amount of organic matter and percentage base

Table 1. Change in soil pH as affected by different treatments and period (day) of submergence

Treatment	Haplaquepts soil (Alluvial)						Haplustalfs soil (Laterite)					
	0	7	14	21	28	35	0	7	14	21	28	35
N_0O_0	7.83	7.95	7.70	7.54	7.32	7.15	5.64	5.72	6.20	6.30	6.72	6.96
N_1O_0	7.72	7.80	7.56	7.40	7.28	7.20	5.50	5.66	5.78	6.01	6.70	6.91
N_2O_0	7.69	7.77	7.58	7.50	7.35	7.18	5.40	5.57	5.61	5.72	6.30	6.87
U_1O_0	7.96	7.72	7.65	7.60	7.48	7.25	5.73	6.12	6.48	6.65	6.72	6.96
U_2O_0	8.04	7.81	7.72	7.52	7.40	7.31	5.80	6.24	6.56	6.64	6.78	7.07
N_0O_1	7.94	7.30	7.25	6.94	7.13	7.23	5.68	5.60	5.94	6.26	6.67	6.90
N_1O_1	7.63	7.30	7.22	7.07	6.98	7.03	5.59	5.44	5.89	6.14	6.50	6.86
N_2O_1	7.52	7.29	7.20	7.10	6.97	7.01	5.42	5.32	5.73	6.08	6.44	6.85
U_1O_1	8.00	7.14	7.10	7.06	7.14	7.20	5.75	5.68	6.17	6.45	6.80	6.93
U_2O_1	8.05	7.25	7.17	7.01	7.12	7.22	5.79	5.73	6.25	6.52	6.77	7.02
N_0O_2	7.88	7.08	6.54	6.33	6.55	7.10	5.65	5.41	5.90	6.20	6.58	6.85
N_1O_2	7.66	7.06	6.49	6.35	6.51	6.87	5.46	5.35	5.83	6.01	6.35	6.77
N_2O_2	7.59	7.18	6.51	6.24	6.48	6.90	5.41	5.20	5.78	5.98	6.40	6.81
U_1O_2	7.95	6.92	6.53	6.40	6.65	7.08	5.60	5.47	5.86	6.25	6.61	6.80
U_2O_2	8.03	6.88	6.61	6.44	6.50	6.93	5.68	5.60	5.92	6.22	6.64	6.94

Table 2. Change in redox potential (E_h , mV) of soil affected by different treatments and period (day) of submergence

Treatment	Haplaquepts soil (Alluvial)						Haplustalfs soil (Laterite)					
	0	7	14	21	28	35	0	7	14	21	28	35
N ₀ O ₀	148	102	88	-75	-112	-125	120	96	82	64	-72	-90
N ₁ O ₀	145	115	97	-64	-92	-108	128	103	87	75	-68	-82
N ₂ O ₀	152	116	108	-58	-80	-100	131	112	94	76	-64	-80
U ₁ O ₀	127	94	80	-98	-118	-124	112	89	54	-81	-98	-109
U ₂ O ₀	138	90	76	-104	-113	-130	107	82	52	-80	-106	-118
N ₀ O ₁	127	75	-85	-120	-143	-154	110	75	38	-90	-112	-137
N ₁ O ₁	134	87	-96	-118	-137	-150	117	81	46	-75	-105	-131
N ₂ O ₁	141	93	-85	-120	-135	-146	122	90	50	-80	-102	-126
U ₁ O ₁	125	63	-112	-133	-146	-161	106	72	-92	-118	-132	-148
U ₂ O ₁	118	65	-110	-130	-151	-168	102	64	-90	-127	-139	-155
N ₀ O ₂	118	-81	-116	-132	-150	-167	105	46	-85	-120	-135	-150
N ₁ O ₂	123	-76	-100	-128	-141	-160	95	66	-87	-116	-130	-138
N ₂ O ₂	129	-64	-106	-125	-144	-157	98	73	-82	-121	-134	-147
U ₁ O ₂	107	-100	-121	-142	-161	-182	90	53	-114	-134	-155	-166
U ₂ O ₂	105	-108	-120	-137	-165	-187	87	49	-115	-140	-160	-175

Table 3. Change in nitrate concentration of soil in different incubation periods (day)

Treatment	Haplaquepts soil (Alluvial)						Haplustalfs soil (Laterite)					
	0	7	14	21	28	35	0	7	14	21	28	35
N ₀ O ₀	0.56	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
N ₁ O ₀	24.26	10.12	4.08	1.66	0.00	0.00	26.12	11.43	4.71	1.95	0.00	0.00
N ₂ O ₀	55.34	23.55	9.84	4.04	1.65	0.00	57.45	24.60	10.20	4.28	1.76	0.00
U ₁ O ₀	6.65	2.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.84	2.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
U ₂ O ₀	11.42	4.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	12.15	5.09	2.09	0.00	0.00	0.00
N ₀ O ₁	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
N ₁ O ₁	22.90	5.84	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	26.20	7.53	2.06	0.00	0.00	0.00
N ₂ O ₁	53.07	12.56	2.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	56.80	16.94	4.01	1.10	0.00	0.00
U ₁ O ₁	6.71	1.61	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.87	1.87	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
U ₂ O ₁	11.30	2.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	12.10	3.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
N ₀ O ₂	0.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.61	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
N ₁ O ₂	23.85	4.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	25.97	5.73	1.18	0.00	0.00	0.00
N ₂ O ₂	55.15	10.35	2.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	57.30	11.86	2.33	0.00	0.00	0.00
U ₁ O ₂	6.68	1.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.80	1.38	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
U ₂ O ₂	11.06	2.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	12.10	2.42	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00

saturation than in the latter. Application of nitrates as KNO₃ was found to reduce the rate of decrease in E_h values. The results also show that the application of KNO₃ prevented a rapid decline in E_h values which is also reported by Reddy and Patrick². Whereas the application of prilled urea caused a greater decrease in the E_h values. This observation finds support from the results of Saha *et al.*⁷.

Kinetics of nitrate reduction : The results (Table 3) reveal that the NO₃-N is completely reduced by the end of 21 days of submergence in both the soils where organic matter as starch was not applied. Whereas, the reduction was completed by the end of 14 days of submergence where starch was applied. Other workers also reported⁸ that the nitrate nitrogen disappears rapidly in submerged soils and this might be due to the presence of facultative organisms that converts NO₃-N to N-containing gases at low O₂ tension¹. The delayed disappearance of NO₃-N in both the soils without the addition of easily oxidisable organic

matter, starch could be attributed to the lack of supply of sufficient energy for the growth of denitrifying microorganisms. Senapati *et al.*⁹ expressed similar views that the addition of organic matter under submerged condition enhances the nitrate reduction process. The decrease in the concentration of NO₃-N with the progress of submergence followed an exponential pattern suggesting first order reaction kinetics. The results of the present investigation are in conformity with that reported earlier¹⁰.

The results (Table 4) show that the addition of starch increases the values of the velocity constants (K) and decreased the half-life periods ($t_{1/2}$). The magnitude of such changes, however, varies with the type of soils, nature of organic matter and period of submergence. The velocity constants and half-life periods were found to vary from 0.118 to 0.240 day⁻¹ and 2.86 to 5.87 days in Haplaquepts soils respectively, whereas the changes of the same in Haplustalfs were varied from 0.108 to 0.230 day⁻¹ and 3.01

to 6.41 days respectively. In Haplaquepts soil, relatively higher values of velocity constant and shorter half-life period were obtained than that of Haplustalfs. Moreover, the intensity of reduction in Haplaquepts soil was more pronounced than that of Haplustalfs and this might have led to a greater concentration of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ in the latter soil. The results also suggest that the faster disappearance of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ in the Haplaquepts soil might be due to the presence of higher amount of initial organic carbon content than that of the Haplustalfs. Similar results have also been reported by Srivastava and Srivastava¹¹.

Table 4. Velocity constant (K) and half-life period ($t_{1/2}$) of nitrate in soils as affected by various treatments

Treatment	Haplaquepts soil (Alluvial)		Haplustalfs soil (Laterite)	
	K (day^{-1})	$t_{1/2}$ (day)	K (day^{-1})	$t_{1/2}$ (day)
N_0O_0	0.118	5.87	0.108	6.41
N_1O_0	0.127	5.46	0.121	5.73
N_2O_0	0.124	5.59	0.123	5.63
U_1O_0	0.128	5.41	0.126	5.50
U_2O_0	0.122	5.68	0.124	5.59
N_0O_1	0.120	5.77	0.110	6.30
N_1O_1	0.195	3.55	0.179	3.87
N_2O_1	0.208	3.33	0.187	3.71
U_1O_1	0.204	3.40	0.186	3.73
U_2O_1	0.207	3.35	0.190	3.65
N_0O_2	0.120	5.77	0.110	6.30
N_1O_2	0.242	2.86	0.218	3.17
N_2O_2	0.239	2.90	0.226	3.07
U_1O_2	0.237	2.92	0.227	3.05
U_2O_2	0.240	2.89	0.230	3.01

The results also reveal that the changes in pH in Haplaquepts soil show a significant negative correlation with the changes in $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ concentration at 0 and 7 days after submergence having r value of -0.78^* and -0.68^* , while that of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ concentration in Haplustalfs soil with pH changes show a significant negative correlation with r value of -0.82^* and -0.75^* respectively.

Experimental

A laboratory experiment simulating lowland rice field condition was carried out with Haplustalfs and Haplaquepts, collected from Bolpur and Kalyani respectively. The characteristics of Haplaquepts and Haplustalfs are pH, 7.9 and 5.0; organic C, 0.85 and 0.38%; CEC [$\text{cmol}(\text{p}^+)$ kg^{-1}], 26.32 and 6.40 and $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, 0.50 and 0.56 mg kg^{-1} respectively. Each soil (10 g) was placed in a series of incubation tubes and starch was added at two levels, i.e. at the rate of 0.5 (O_1) and 1% (O_2) by weight of the soil. Subsequently, nitrogen as urea (U) and KNO_3 (N) at the rate of 30 (N_1 or U_1) and 60 (N_2 or U_2) mg kg^{-1} was also added. There were altogether 15 treatment combinations, and these were used for each soil.

The experiments were conducted in a completely randomised design (CRD) with each treatment replicated twice. Then all the tubes receiving the respective treatments were kept for incubation at room temperature after adding deionised water to a level of 2.0 ± 0.5 cm above the soil surface. The level of water was maintained throughout the period of incubation by adding requisite amount of deionised water. At the end of each incubation period the concentration of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ in each soil and overlying flood water was measured⁵. The velocity constant (K) and half-life period ($t_{1/2}$) were calculated by following the linear regression of $\log(a-x)$ at time (t) as

$$K = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a}{(a-x)}$$

where, a is the initial concentration, and $(a-x)$ the concentration at time t .

A separate set of incubations with two soils using same treatments to that of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ under similar conditions was also maintained simultaneously to study the changes of pH and redox potential (E_h) of the soils. The pH was measured potentiometrically with the help of glass and calomel electrodes in 1 : 2.5 soil : water ratio. The redox potential of the submerged soil was measured³ by inserting a bright platinum electrode (sealed in a glass tube) into soil for 0.5 h for equilibrium before recording the potential difference against a standard saturated calomel electrode, both being connected to a potentiometer having E_h scale.

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